

PRINCIPLES OF FORMING PHYSICAL ABILITIES OF 4-5 CLASS PUPILS OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15318587>

Abstract. *This article addresses the issues of developing the physical abilities of 4th and 5th grade pupils through extracurricular activities. The aim of the research is to determine the effectiveness of extracurricular activities in developing physical abilities and to provide recommendations for optimizing this process. It presents an analysis of scientific literature on physical education, practical observations, and the results of experimental research.*

Keywords: *physical abilities, extracurricular activities, 4th-5th grade students, physical education, speed, strength, endurance, agility, flexibility, physiological maturation, motor skills, adaptability skills.*

Introduction. In our country, the necessary conditions and opportunities have been created for the upbringing of a healthy and harmonious generation, for the realization of the creative and intellectual potential of young people, for the upbringing of our country's young male and female as well-developed and harmonious individuals.

Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at the formation of physical and volitional qualities in children, their mental and physical preparation for labor and defense of the Motherland, and is manifested as an integral part of social education. The existing social conditions based on highly developed production indicate the need to educate a young generation that is physically strong, capable of working with high productivity in the production process, not afraid of difficulties, and also always ready to defend the Motherland

Literature analysis. The problem of developing pupils' thinking, creative organization and activation of the educational process is covered in detail in the studies of A.Gulomov, M.Haqberdiev, T.Ziyodova, S.Yaminova, M.Saidov, B.Adizov, Ya.Rakhmonov. In the study of Q.Yuldoshev, ways of organizing literature lessons on the basis of pedagogical cooperation were developed. M.Makhmutov, V.Okon, R.Ibragimov studied ways of creating problem situations in the educational process and on this basis increasing the effectiveness of students' educational activities. The process of independent work and its impact on students' educational activities and thinking was studied by O.Rozikov, R.Mallayev, A.Gulomov, T.Niyozmetova, N.Sattorova, S.Matchonov, L.Mirdjalalova, Y.Rakhmonov. The problem of organizing the educational process on the basis of games can be seen in the studies of R. Tolipova, J. Tolipova, A. Bobomurodova, F. Kadirova. A. Choriyev philosophically analyzed the activity of independent thinking as a main component of individual independence. Physical education is a process aimed at the comprehensive development of the younger generation, shaping its consciousness, behavior and worldview based on socio-historical experience. [3]

The laws of physiological maturation of the organism, the spiritual development of a person, the achievements of philosophical and pedagogical thoughts, as well as the level of social

culture give a general direction to the goal of physical education. In the famous words of L. Tolstoy: “To be spiritually healthy, one must be physically fit.[2]

Research methodology. General and special literature on the subject, the physical culture system of our country and the current physical culture DTS recommend the use of the following forms of physical education classes for students in general education schools. These are:

- classes in the form of educational work
- classes in the form of extracurricular work (organized by the school physical culture team (MJMJ),
- health-improving classes as part of the school day,
- classes in extracurricular institutions,
- physical education and physical culture classes in the family,
- classes in state and non-state educational and sports institutions.

Activities suitable for 4th grade children can be divided into the following groups according to the development of physical qualities:

1. Activities that develop agility and flexibility in children;
2. Activities that increase strength in children.
3. Activities that develop endurance and agility in children [2].

Analysis and results. According to the results of the study, the physical abilities of 4th-5th grade students are developed to different degrees. It was found that students who regularly participate in extracurricular activities have higher physical fitness indicators than those who do not. In particular, significant differences were observed in speed, endurance and agility abilities [2].

In the movement games and relay races held in additional classes with primary school students, competition exercises were often used (walking and running to catch the ball, passing the ball along a line, column and circle, dribbling the ball on the move, throwing the ball). Throwing the ball into the ring with the head and both hands, pulling the rope, running around four or five rings or cubes, flags placed on the floor at a distance of 1.5 m from each other) [2].

In the warm season, games and relay races are held outdoors (in the stadium), and in the cold season, in the gym and outdoors. Each additional session includes 7 to 10 minutes of active games and relay races. In additional sessions, frontal, flow, and circular methods of performing exercises are used to increase the physical activity of children [2].

The following recommendations have been developed to increase the effectiveness of extracurricular activities in developing physical abilities:

- Organizing classes taking into account the age characteristics of children.
- Using a variety of physical exercises in classes.
- Choosing sports taking into account the interests of students.
- Involving parents in classes and ensuring their support [1].

The importance of extracurricular activities: Provides students with the opportunity to consolidate the knowledge gained in physical education classes. Creates additional conditions for the development of physical abilities. Strengthens children's health and attracts them to sports.

Theoretically substantiating the problem of forming physical abilities of 4th grade primary school students in extracurricular activities, revealing ways to implement it in the process of forming physical abilities of primary school students made it possible to determine the goals, objectives and content of experimental work [2]

At this stage of the research, we set ourselves the goal: to empirically identify the pedagogical conditions necessary for future educators to form their readiness to manage the development of children's physical abilities.

We propose a physical development system for the formation of physical abilities of primary school students. This system is holistic, sufficiently growing, integrative, and includes the stages of diagnosis, information-motivation, design-organization and generalization.

The purpose of our study was to solve the following tasks:

Assimilation indicators of the experimental group:

$$(1) \begin{cases} X_i & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ n_i & 101 & 123 & 12 \end{cases} \quad n = \sum_{i=1}^3 n_i = 236$$

Assimilation indicators of the control group:

$$(2) \begin{cases} Y_j & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ m_j & 64 & 97 & 75 \end{cases} \quad m = \sum_{j=1}^3 m_j = 236$$

In order to facilitate statistical analysis, we calculate the frequency of repetitions (frequencies) of the above variation series using $p_i = \frac{n_i}{n}$ va $q_j = \frac{m_j}{m}$ the appropriate statistical probability formulas.

$$(3) \begin{cases} X_i & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ p_i & 0,43 & 0,52 & 0,05 \end{cases} \quad \sum_{i=1}^3 p_i = 1$$

$$(4) \begin{cases} Y_j & 3 & 2 & 1 \\ q_j & 0,27 & 0,41 & 0,32 \end{cases} \quad \sum_{j=1}^3 q_j = 1$$

We begin the statistical analysis by calculating and comparing the average assimilation of both groups. The average assimilation indicators gave the following results:

$$\bar{X} = \sum_{i=1}^3 p_i X_i = 0,43 \cdot 3 + 0,52 \cdot 2 + 1 \cdot 0,05 = 1,29 + 1,04 + 0,05 = 2,38$$

In percent $\bar{X}\% = \frac{2,38}{3} \cdot 100\% = 79,3\%$

$$\bar{Y} = \sum_{j=1}^3 q_j Y_j = 0,27 \cdot 3 + 0,41 \cdot 2 + 0,32 \cdot 1 = 0,81 + 0,82 + 0,32 = 1,95$$

In percent $\bar{Y}\% = \frac{1,95}{3} \cdot 100\% = 65,0\%$

Thus, the assimilation in the experimental groups is 14.3% higher than the average assimilation in the control groups (79.3 - 65.0). This, in turn, means $\frac{79,3\%}{65,0\%} = 1,22$ an equal excess.

So, at the end of the experimental work, the respondent's knowledge indicators increased by an average of 14.3%.

As can be seen from the table above, pupils in the experimental group achieved significant growth in all physical abilities during the study. In the control group, the growth rates were much lower. This shows that extracurricular activities are an effective tool in developing the physical abilities of pupils in grades 4-5.[2]

Scientific innovation: A comprehensive model for assessing the impact of extracurricular activities on the physical abilities of students has been developed. New methodological approaches have been proposed to increase the effectiveness of extracurricular activities (for example, an individual approach, the use of game elements, ensuring the participation of parents). It was found that extracurricular activities have a positive effect not only on the physical, but also on the psychological development of children (increased self-confidence, increased stress resistance, development of teamwork skills). In particular, the increase in the pull-up rate on the horizontal bar by 40% in the experimental group indicates the important role of extracurricular activities in the development of strength abilities. Also, an increase in the speed of running for 30 meters by 7% demonstrates the effect of training on the development of speed abilities.[1]

Statistical analysis showed that there was a significant difference between the results of the experimental and control groups at the end of the study ($p < 0.05$). This confirms the effectiveness of extracurricular activities in developing physical abilities. The results obtained are consistent with the results of previous studies and once again confirm the important role of extracurricular activities in the physical development of children. Extracurricular activities help students develop their physical abilities, as well as form a healthy lifestyle, be disciplined, and work in a team. The results of this study can serve as a basis for developing recommendations for organizing extracurricular activities in schools and increasing their effectiveness.

Conclusion. This study was devoted to the study of the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of physical abilities of 4-5th grade students through extracurricular activities. During the study, the role of physical abilities in the development of children, the advantages of extracurricular activities and the principles of their organization were identified. Also, through practical research, the impact of extracurricular activities on the basic physical abilities of students was assessed.

The results showed that extracurricular activities play an important role in the development of students' speed, strength, endurance, agility and flexibility. The growth indicators observed in the experimental group confirm the effectiveness of extracurricular activities. The factors identified during the study, in particular, the suitability of the activities for the age characteristics of children, the use of various exercises and the interesting organization of the activities, have a positive effect on the development of physical abilities.

Since only 4-5th grade students participated in this study, the results obtained cannot be fully applied to other age groups. Also, only basic physical abilities were assessed during the study, other physical qualities (for example, balance, coordination) were not studied. This study confirms the importance of extracurricular activities in the physical development of children and creates a basis for new research in this area. The results of the study contribute to the improvement of physical education in schools and the formation of a healthy lifestyle for children.

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